

Habitat loss and biodiversity loss go hand in hand in Bangladesh: Causes and Consequences

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Abstract

The natural forests of Bangladesh are decreasing at an alarming rate due to high population density, sharply skewed distribution of lands, and the overexploitation of forest resources. The natural forests have become critically fragmented to the point where they are considered unlikely to maintain a rich level of biodiversity, nor support viable populations of natural and native species. The study aimed to identify the causes and consequences of habitat destruction in Bangladesh. In addition, the relationship between habitat loss and biodiversity loss was assessed. Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. It was revealed that habitat destructions occur in three ways: whole ecosystems are destroyed or converted into farmland, exotic forests and settlements; ecosystems are partially removed, creating 'islands' surrounded by farmland, and ecosystems are degraded by the loss of species and disruption of their ecological processes. Over-population, faulty land ownership patterns and shifting cultivation are prime causal factors of habitat loss. The immediate consequences of habitat destruction are deforestation; loss of existing species; loss of species richness; increased rarity; and loss of genetic diversity. When the habitat becomes more fragmented and isolated, the organisms in them are finding it increasingly difficult to survive, which leads to ultimate extinction. The study outlined integrated conservation management to comply with the core of 'The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)'.

Keywords: Habitat destruction, overexploitation, native biodiversity, extinction, fragmentation, integrated conservation management, The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)

Introduction

Our planet is changing continuously, causing habitats to be altered and modified (Palombo 2021; Fischer & Lindenmayer 2007). Tropical and sub-tropical forests are always subject to destructive natural forces -cyclones landslides, floods, mudflows, volcanic eruptions, fire, drought, and climate change (Chandrappa *et al* 2011; Jentsch *et al.* 2021; Urama & Ozor 2010). These factors are overwhelmed by anthropogenic disturbances. These forests are being logged everywhere at a very high rate. Approximately 50% of forest lands have no forest coverage because of human activities (Houghton 1999). Deforestation is not a recent human activity in tropical forests. These were inhabited by humans thousands of years back. Charcoal deposits indicate human activity in the sediments of many tropical forests which we know as virgin forests. Granules of various starchy root vegetables were found on 5000 – 7000-year-old stone grinding tools of Panama, indicating that people were cultivating crops in forests from ancient times (Piperno *et al.* 2000).

The mega biodiversity hotspots of the world contain a high degree of endemism and are undergoing gradual loss of habitats (Hughes 2017). A maximum portion of these hotspots is located in tropical forests, which are considered the most endangered (Silva *et al.* 2002). Habitat degradation is one of the major causes of biodiversity loss. The mega hotspots now consist of a very smaller portion of their former area and primary vegetation (Myers 1990). Laurance *et al.* (2021) reported that Bazilian Amazon Rainforests lose at the rate of 1.38 million ha/yr to 11.98 million ha/yr. The highest rate of deforestation is occurring in South Asia, where 70% of the areas have been deforested. All tropical forests of South Asia will disappear in less than 50 years if the same rate of deforestation continues. The hotspots will lose 40% of their species if current rates of habitat loss continue, even if for only another decade. These forests will not last beyond the mid-21st century (Sodhi *et al.* 2004).

Huge population pressure and widespread poverty are the main frontiers of habitat degradation in Bangladesh. Due to high population density and sharply skewed distribution of lands, forest resources are overexploited (Rahman 2021). Per capita forestland in the country is around 0.0009ha (Islam *et al.* 2023) and the existing natural forests are decreasing at a rate varying from 2.1% /yr. to 3.3% /yr. (Mia 2003). Massive habitat destruction occurred in the Sal forests of Bangladesh (Rahman 2023a; Rahman *et al.* 2007, Rahman and Vacik 2009). The recurrent anthropogenic disturbances in the Sal forests have rendered the system inhospitable for the

regeneration and growth of wild plant associates, causing a net loss in plant diversity (Rahman *et al.* 2009, 2010, Rahman & Vacik 2010). No single part of the Sal forests can be found as undisturbed natural forests. Logging, regeneration destruction, litter sweeping, animal grazing and soil disturbances are common in all forest areas (Rahman *et al.* 2009). Recreational activities like picnics are an additional human pressure in the Sal forests (Rahman & Vacik 2009). One can hardly find native species in these forests.

The hydroelectricity project, ethnic conflict, encroachment, and jhum cultivation are the main causes of hill deforestation (Khisa & Mohiuddin 2015). Poverty, profit-making, natural disaster, salinity and sedimentation are the major causes of Sundarbans degradation (Rahman 2023 b, c, d, e, f). The vast degradation of Sundari trees is also caused by high salinity (Rahman 2020). Different types of diseases of the trees are also accountable for the deforestation in the Sundarbans. Illegal logging is also responsible for deforestation in the Sundarbans (Rahman 2022 a, b). Lack of alternative livelihood pushes the coastal people to depend on mangrove forest products (Rahman 2022 a, b).

Hog deer, water buffalo, swamp deer, Javan rhinoceros, single-horned rhinoceros and the mugger crocodile became extinct at the beginning of the last century Sundarbans due to habitat destruction (Ghosh & Mondal 2016). Different studies show that all our natural old forests have become critically fragmented to the point where they are considered unlikely to maintain a rich level of biodiversity, nor support viable populations of natural and native species of flora and fauna (Rahman *et al.* 2007). Abundant species have become occasional, occasional become rare, rare become very rare and very rare become extinct (Rahman *et al.* 2009). Once upon a time, the Sal forests of Bangladesh were the sweet home of beautiful Capped Langur. Now it is threatened by habitat loss and has become an IUCN-red-listed species (Ahmed *et al.* 2019). Less than a hundred years ago, tigers prowled all across the Indian subcontinent. But increasing habitat loss has contracted the tiger's former range (Aziz *et al.* 2013, 2017; Barlow 2009). Tigers need large territories for roaming and preying. About 95% population of Western Hoolock Gibbons in Bangladesh will be lost over the next two decades based on the current effects of habitat destruction (Uddin *et al.* 2020; Islam *et al.* 2006). Now Asian Elephant is the largest critically endangered terrestrial animal in Bangladesh (Hossain *et al.* 2023). The major cause of the decline in the wild elephant population in Bangladesh is habitat destruction (Islam 2023). There has been rampant

habitat loss of Marbled and Fishing cats throughout the Sal forests over the past 20 years (Rahman 2023a). Habitat destruction throughout Bangladesh is occurring at an alarming rate to the peril of biodiversity (Rahman 2023 g, h).

The study aimed to identify the causes and consequences of habitat destruction in Bangladesh. In addition, the relationship between habitat loss and biodiversity loss was assessed.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from different sources of literature. Five focus group discussions were done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to understand to identify the causes and consequences of the habitat loss. Based on the respondents' perceptions the interrelation between habitat loss and biodiversity loss was assessed. In addition, the respondents were asked to find out the solutions. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Causes of habitat destruction

The respondents opined that habitat loss occurs in three ways: 1) whole ecosystems are destroyed or converted into farmland, exotic forests and settlements; 2) ecosystems are partially removed, creating 'islands' surrounded by farmland; 3) ecosystems are degraded by the loss of species and disruption of their ecological processes. Habitats can either disappear completely or they may become degraded and/or fragmented. The loss of natural forests and the fragmentation of remaining areas into progressively smaller patches is a significant global trend. Habitat degradation occurs in different ways, like in patches (e.g.), in waves (e.g., by urbanization) or linear (e.g., by construction of roads).

The respondents argued that the natural forests in Bangladesh are often regarded as useless unless they can be used for crop production or exploited as sources of wood or rubber. They are also treated as vast sources of land for the relief of social pressures and incomes for the poverty-stricken. The costs of such deforestation are ignored or seen as tolerable in comparison to "non-utilization." The following factors identified by the respondents for the habitat destruction in Bangladesh: 1) over-population, 2) faulty land ownership pattern, 3) shifting cultivation, 4) illegal and commercial logging, 5) high demand for timber, 6) scarcity of fuel wood, 7) high extraction

of non-wood products, 8) destruction of natural vegetation, 9) soil disturbances, 10) inadequate valuation of forests as resources, 11) inadequate protection, 12) establishment of infrastructures and transport networks, 13) extractive activities, 14) inappropriate interventions, 15) construction of dams for hydropower sources, 16) poverty, 17) excessive extraction of non-timbering plants, 18) lack of philosophical and ethical attitudes, 18) animal grazing, 19) litter sweeping, 20) encroachment and land grabbing, 21) economic attitudes, 22) greed and corruption, 23 social structures, 24) wars and social conflicts, 25) tourism, 26) introduction of exotic species, 27) overexploitation; and 28) brick field.

Consequences of habitat destruction

Based on the respondents' perceptions, the consequences of habitat destruction in Bangladesh are enlisted as follows: 1) deforestation; 2) losing of existing species; 3) decreasing vegetation coverage; 4) accelerating soil erosion; 5) loss of species richness; 6) increasing rarity; 7) loss of genetic diversity; 8) loss of evolutionary potential; 9) changes in water cycles; 10) changes in water tables; 11) conversion in pure stands; 12) difficulty in aforestation; 13) destruction of natural regeneration, 14) climate change; 15) increasing of physical disturbances; 16) loss of ecosystem services, 17) disruption of livelihoods of indigenous people; 18) social instabilities, 19) economic losses; 20) increasing susceptibility of pathogen infection and insect infestation; 21) loss of forest productivity; 22) decreasing of forest non-wood products; 24) increasing of environmental refugees; and 25) affecting habitats in proximity to degraded habitat.

Relationship between habitat loss and biodiversity loss

The exact relationship between deforestation and loss of biodiversity was assessed by the respondents. There are many factors in this complex relationship. The removal of a few trees or a few species from a forest may cause a cascade of species losses due to changes in the microenvironment. The removal of a " keystone" species may disrupt the highly complex interrelationships among species. Extinction rates depend on many factors such as forest type, soil type, level of anthropogenic disturbances, degree of endemism, extent of land degradation, and so forth. When forests become more fragmented and isolated, the organisms in them are finding it increasingly difficult to survive. Small populations will be unlikely to persevere as their environments change and they are exposed to increasing hunting/gathering pressures and stress. Both population size and species richness decrease as the habitat abundance decreases. Rare and

patchily distributed species requiring a large range seem particularly susceptible to habitat destruction. Larger patches contain more species than small patches. Small fragments experience more extinction and receive fewer immigrants. Small fragments or islands that are more remote from the mainland or source population have fewer species because the extinction rate is the same but the immigration rate is lower. Most of the species are composed of relatively few individuals, randomly distributed throughout the geographical range of that species, or located in one small area only (endemism). Many tropical forest species require large and undisturbed forests; they cannot thrive in degraded habitats. The fragmented forests do not contain the full range of forest species. Deforestation involves the conversion of continuous forest to the remnant of forest patches set in a matrix of non-forest vegetation. The altered microclimate becomes unsuitable for certain species by increasing mortality rates near the edge and reducing recruitment to their populations. The forest ecosystem is often characterized by a heavy dependency on mutualistic species interactions for its stability. Many plant species in the forests are reliant on animals as agents of dispersal for either pollen or seeds or both. Habitat destruction causes the extinction of certain important pollinating or seed-dispersing animals which severely limits regeneration of rare plant species and hence initiates an extinction vortex. Heavily fragmented forests do not support a home range for larger species. Larger species may have trouble finding habitat in not sufficient density to support a home range in heavily fragmented forests. Fragment size, degree of isolation and time since excision from the continuous forest directly influence the biodiversity of fragmented habitat. Species also tend to suffer from genetic drift and inbreeding in degraded habitats. Migration is an important phenomenon for the maintenance of high local levels of diversity in tropical forests. In distant fragments, the rare species will die out relatively rapidly and not be replaced by other species because of a failure of immigration. Fragment edges are inhospitable to most forest species. The deforested matrix of a fragmented landscape is often dominated by alien species because few of the native species are tolerant of the extremely exposed conditions in the exposed areas. Habitat loss is the primary cause of species endangerment.

Integrated conservation management

The core of 'The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)' is the promotion of an integrated approach to natural resource management on large landscapes and to biodiversity conservation through enhancing wildlife habitat and reducing habitat fragmentation. Integrated conservation is

warranted for the conservation of biodiversity; extracting forest products sustainably; preserving genetic resources; maintaining hydrological functions; improving air quality; stabilizing climate; retention of soil fertility; controlling pests; proper pollination; aesthetic factors and recreation; wilderness; and ethical values. The integrated conservation includes the following activities:

- * Reducing human population growth
- * Improving land use pattern
- * Sustainable forest development
- * Introducing biological corridors
- * Maintaining buffer zones in between core and peripheral zones
- * Changing policies towards forests
- * Involving indigenous peoples and traditional communities in the conservation programme
- * Protecting forest lands
- * Strengthening forest monitoring, research and development, education, and capacity building to maintain a “cradle” of biodiversity within the core areas of each protected forests
- * Improving agricultural methods and productivity
- * Improving legal systems
- * Stopping the introduction of alien invasive species
- * Gap filling by rare tree species
- * Afforestation and reforestation by native and natural species
- * Facilitating natural regeneration in degraded forests
- * Leaving denuded forest lands untouched for 20 years to promote the natural succession of forests
- * Stopping further clear felling and illegal logging
- * Protecting natural regenerations (seedling, sapling and juvenile trees) from cutting

- * Introducing pioneer and early successional species in the degraded forests
- * Taking effective actions against the encroachers and land grabbers
- * Establishing gene banks to conserve the gene pool of endangered species
- * Bringing endangered animals in captivity for breeding
- * Reducing social and economic imbalances
- * Minimizing anthropogenic disturbances
- * Establishing national centres for the conservation of threatened and endangered species
- * Increasing basic research on the impact of forest degradation
- * Considering conservation programme as an asset in economic calculations
- * Reforming trade policies
- * Taking appropriate actions against animal poaching
- * Poverty alleviation in the adjacent areas of forests
- * Emphasizing community-based conservation
- * Establishing more protected areas
- * Searching for alternative fuel sources in the forest areas
- * Creating alternative livelihoods for the indigenous people
- * Initiating Rehabilitation programme for the illegal loggers
- * Improving environmental education
- * Taking care of secondary and successional forests

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